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Continuous GNSS Geodetic Networks. A Powerful Tool for Monitoring and Understanding Complex Volcanic Environments: The Case of Santorini Volcano During the Seismic Crisis of 2024-2025

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Abstract

Late summer of 2024 an unusual raise of the seismic activity was observed inside the Caldera of Santorini Volcanic Complex. This was the first time since the 2011-2012 unrest period that increased seismicity was recorded inside the Santorini Caldera. Together with the raise of the seismicity, daily GNSS data from a permanent station in Imerovigli (station SANT) as well as two other operating stations in Santorini, exhibited change on the kinematic behavior of the Island. The typical SE directional motion of the SANT station (with respect to ITRF2014) observed the last decade was altered to a strong ENE motion. Moreover, increased uplift started taking place in the SANT station with a rate of almost 80mm/yr, an order of amplitude higher than the typical of 2-3 mm/yr of the last years. This kinematic motion could be explained by volcanic activity inside the caldera, modeled as a typical Mogi point source.

However, at the end of January 2025, almost 6 months after the initiation of the activity inside the caldera, there was an abrupt migration of the seismicity NE of Santorini, in the marine area between Thira and Amorgos Islands. During a period of almost a month (February 2025) intense seismic activity was recorded in the marine area around the islet of Anydros, located ~25km NE of Thira. Several seismic events of $M > 3$ were recorded almost every day, during that period, with the larger event to be of $M 5.3$. This intense seismicity was accompanied by strong ground deformation on the broad area of South Aegean. As was expected, the most intense ground deformation was observed in Thira Island and in Anydros Islet. However, the type of motion in SANT cGNSS station was of completely different type compare to the previous period (while the seismicity was located inside the Caldera). The SANT station showed a strong North motional component and intense subsidence. It has to be noticed that the daily amplitude of the ground deformation reached values up to 10mm/day during the peak of the seismic crisis (10-15 of February). Moreover, GNSS data from the surrounding islands, as is Ios and Naxos to the North of Thira exhibited changes in their kinematic behavior, highlighting the intense activity that was taking place in the marine area of Anydros Islet.

The strong ground deformation decreased around the end of February 2025, almost a month after its initiation. Since then, it appears that the rate of ground deformation has significantly decreased in both horizontal and vertical component. The decrease of ground displacement coincided with the decrease in the seismicity, that has been expressed not only with smaller number of events per day, but also and of smaller amplitude, with the events of $\sim M 3$ to be less than the previous one month long period.

A major issue during this crisis was the identification of the seismic activity; it was of volcanic or tectonic character / origin? In the complex environment of South Aegean, where the Santorini Volcanic complex is located, there is not an easy or unique answer to such issues. Major tectonic zones, as is the Amorgos area (with a history of strong earthquakes), volcanic centers as is the Kameni Islet and the submarine Kolubo volcano, create an extremely complex geological environment that requires a multidisciplinary approach in order to comprehend it. To better understand, explain and monitor the ongoing processes in the broad area of south Aegean the geodetic and seismological academic

and research community of Greece took action establishing a dense network of continuous GNSS stations, as well as seismological stations. In this common effort several institutes from abroad also collaborate and joint efforts with the Greek institutes. The main scope of this effort is to achieve a better spatial coverage of the area, with permanent operating stations, and be able not only to monitor the daily progress of the deformation and seismological crisis but also to foresee its evolution. As result of this joint effort, it was the establishment, and/or re-start of more the 20 permanent GNSS stations in the broad area of South Aegean Sea. The new GNSS stations that were established in the island of Thira, Thirasia, Ios, Amorgos, Anafi, Sikinos, and in the islets of Anydros and Christiana, together with the existing stations in the surrounding islands that were operated by other private entities (Hellenic Cadastre HEPOS, Metrica SA, JGC SA, TreeCompany SA,), together with new sites that were established by other international institutes in collaboration with the Greek ones (ie, CNRS - École Normale Supérieure - PSL, France, INGV, Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia, Italy) and with the support of Earthquake Planning and Protection Organization of Greece (EPPO) will provide on a continuous base all the necessary data in order to monitor this vital area of Greece, will help to better protect the local community and will also provide valuable insight on the geological processes that are taking place in the complex environment of Santorini Volcano, the broad area of South Aegean, as well as along the Hellenic Volcanic Arc. The daily GNSS data from all the operating stations are processed on a near real-time basis, using advanced algorithms, from all the participating institutions providing solutions and information not only for scientific use but also for operational use on the framework of the civil protection actions.

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